

Practice Abstract no. 48

FOODITY - Open Call #2 project - 3FAIR

The FOODITY project launched the second of its two open calls in May 2024 and closed in July 2024. The FOODITY project selected six innovative data-driven projects that develop solutions contributing to more sustainable food systems while boosting citizen data sovereignty. Starting in November 2024, the six projects will receive up to €187,500 to develop their project activities.

One of the selected projects is “3FAIR: FAIR Data, FAIR Food, FAIR Network”

Profile

Project acronym / title	3FAIR FAIR Data, FAIR Food, FAIR Network
Partners (country)	COMMONSLAB KOIN.S.EP. (Greece), Mediterranean Agronomic Institute of Chania (Greece), TERRA VERDE KOIN.S.EP. (Greece)
Project area	Services

Context

Fair-trade and solidarity stores offer products and employment that can provide superior benefit to society as a whole. Thus, it is important to provide them the necessary access to the tools or the knowledge to use digital technologies and to optimally take advantage of their key position as mediator between consumers and producers.

For the fair and solidarity shops to prosper and run more sustainably (economically as well as socially and ecologically), it is important that they market their products efficiently and build a strong trust relationship with consumers, in order for their customers to be willing to pay the premium price.

Furthermore, dialogue between stores and consumers is often informal and does not fully exploit potentially available data, because most stores lack the resources and technical expertise necessary to conduct comprehensive market research and to develop personalised communication strategies. What's more, current popular tools and platforms to aid customer surveys and market research are closed systems that limit citizens' rights to data sovereignty and transferability. This restriction hinders the potential to use personal data for the common good, even when users consent to share their anonymised data.

Objectives

The objective of the 3FAIR solution is to provide a safe virtual space, utilising QR-code technology, to enable consumers to securely share their data with their preferred fair trade stores. By fostering trust among actors, the platform ensures that the food system as a whole receives valuable data from a key stakeholder: the consumers. Simultaneously, the solution enables the store to provide consumers with detailed product information, often sourced directly from the producers, thus allowing consumers to trace the product's journey from farm to fork. This empowers producers, vendors and consumers committed to sustainability, strengthens and expands their networks, and ultimately guides the food system towards better sustainability.

The value of the solution focuses on:

- **Enhanced customer experience:** Personalised recommendations may improve customer satisfaction.
- **Informed decision-making:** Tailored product information aids better choices.
- **Market insights:** Valuable consumer behaviour data optimises inventory and marketing.
- **Strengthened loyalty:** Personalised communication builds stronger relationships, boosting loyalty and repeat purchases.

Impact

The 3FAIR project provides a foundation of trust, an important prerequisite for the transition to a sustainable food system that is essential for behavioural change and motivating citizens to share their data. With trust and understanding, citizens play a more active role in transforming the food system towards sustainability. This creates conditions for increased demand for more "ethical" products, which can lead to a consequent increase in supply. By strengthening the ethical and solidarity-based food trade market, 3FAIR aims to attract new producers and bring about change in the food system.

Retail food stores are central to the food chain, serving as the main access point for consumers to purchase products from producers. Currently, the food retail market is experiencing strong growth, fueled by trends such as increasing consumer preference for private label brands, higher spending on food products, and the rise of supermarket shopping. While fair trade social enterprises are perfectly positioned to link small-scale producers with consumers, they often lack the necessary financial means and expertise to fully capitalize on this potential.

The 3FAIR solution helps overcome these challenges and optimise the communication and distribution processes, ultimately benefiting both producers and consumers. Leveraging these strengths, the solution can drive meaningful changes in the food system, enhancing both producer capabilities and consumer satisfaction.

